

Youth, Climate Change, and the IPCC

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Summary

Today's youth grow up with climate change: they are aware of it, they are affected by it, and they see it as an integral part of their current and future life. But what exactly is their relationship with climate change, and notably with the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)? This is what the Technical Support Unit (TSU) of the IPCC Working Group I (WGI) attempted to determine. Via an online survey, young people from all over the world were questioned about their knowledge and feelings about climate change, as well as their familiarity with the IPCC. The results portray youth as interested in climate issues but also as anxious about the way things might go down. Indeed, if 80% of the participants knew that the IPCC was the United Nations body for collecting and evaluating the science related to climate change, 79% of them would agree with the statement *"Thinking about climate change impacts me emotionally/ makes me anxious"*. They request dialog, answers and tools to light this obscure and uncertain future to come. This report provides the detailed results of the survey as well as some recommendations, with a view to reaching out to youth.

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Context

The IPCC has just started its Seventh Assessment Cycle and the three main reports will be scoped in December 2024. The Working Group I (WGI) Technical Support Unit (TSU) has started various initiatives with the aim to collect information for this important meeting where the content of the main reports of the IPCC Seventh Cycle will be discussed by Experts from all around the world.

As young people are important stakeholders, the WGI TSU wanted to include their input/views and learn more about their feelings, the questions they have about climate change but also understand what they think of the IPCC and how the IPCC can help them and fulfil the youth' request. **Youth** voices on climate change have been rising for about a decade now, starting in 2015 when students skipped school for a strike that happened at the same time as the COP21. We also all know the young climate activist Greta Thunberg who created the Friday strikes for the future, empowering with her actions an entire generation. Since then, millions of young people have participated in strikes and climate actions, shifting public opinion on climate.

Methodology

Target

Definition of youth

In order to be as clear as possible, we needed to set a limit age, since the questionnaire was intended for youth. According to the United Nations¹, youth are between 15 and 24 years old. But according to UN Habitat, youth are between 15 and 32 years old, while the African Youth Charter stated that youth are people between 15 and 35 years old.

Since there was no consensus, we decided to make our age limit an average age from all those international limits and choose 30 years old.

Objectives

The aim of the survey was to answer the following questions:

1. How do young people feel about the climate crisis and their future?
2. Which scientific questions do they have about climate change?
3. How much do they know about the IPCC?
4. How can the IPCC help them and involve them better?

Process

The study was carried out in three main stages:

- ✓ Stage 1: identification of Youth organisations around the world and contact to check their willingness to be part of the study
- ✓ Stage 2: development of an on-line survey and distribution among volunteering Youth organisations (distribution dates: 24 May-5 July 2024)
- ✓ Stage 3: collection of the results, analysis and synthesis

¹ Source: United Nations website <https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/documents/youth/fact-sheets/youth-definition.pdf>

Identifying the organisations

First, a lot of research on the internet was done, in order to collect names of organisations and their contact or focal point details. The keywords used were “Youth and climate” or “youth and environment”, “youth for climate”, “youth climate organisation” or “juventud y clima”. The point was to find youth-led organisations, or organisations which were giving a lot of space for youth’ action and with an environmental approach. We first looked within the YOUNGO² members organisations: their websites were checked, in order to collect their names, purpose, main actions, their leaders and their contact info. This information was compiled in a Microsoft Excel document. Then, the search strategy was to look at their partner organisations' information, which allowed us to find a very large range of environmental oriented youth organisations all around the world.

We then got help from some IPCC members and ex-members who gave us some key contacts, ideas and suggestions about our task, allowing us to reach to the youth climate ambassadors, UN youth advisory group, Science Working Group of YOUNGO and to scientists who were familiar with this topic. After 3 weeks of research, 162 organisations from different regions of the world were identified.

Organisations/coalitions by region

Some of them were coalitions, some were youth delegations, some were local organisations and some were international organisations (with actions located worldwide)³.

The organisations’ main purposes are youth representation, advocacy/leadership training, organisation of youth protest movements, education, local actions, networking and collaboration, youth empowerment, project planning, campaigning and mobilisation.

Most of the organisations had an internet website, where we could find all the information needed. When the website couldn’t be found or wasn’t accessible, we checked on social media. Indeed, most of the time, organisations had a Facebook page (if not, an Instagram account), where all the information required could be easily found.

Development of a survey

See Annex I for the survey

² YOUNGO is the official children and youth constituency of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) [<https://unfccc.int/topics/education-youth/youth/youngo>]

³ A **coalition** is composed of organisations, which join forces under one banner. A **delegation** is composed of organisations’ representatives.

While trying to collect the organisations' info, we developed a questionnaire which could allow us to gather all the information we needed in order to answer our questions.

This questionnaire was an online Microsoft form (the use of this tool was preferred to other ones, less inclusive as not available in all countries) available in English and in French.

Before the survey was finalised, a draft version was prepared and circulated among various testers in order to check its accessibility but also if the questions were clear enough and did cover all the needs. The online questionnaire was composed of 6 sections:

✓ Section 1: Opening section

Introduction to the questionnaire, to its purpose, to its rules (participants should be under 30 years old, deadline to answer, questions in English but the participants can answer in their own language if they precise which language it is before answering...) and to information about the TSU and the data collection.

✓ Section 2: the participant

The objective here was to collect some basic data (age, gender, nationality(ies) and country of residence, the way they got the survey and if they knew the IPCC or not) in order to run statistics and define the various profiles of the respondents.

✓ Section 3: introducing the IPCC

The objective was to understand what the different participants knew or not about the IPCC and whether they trusted the scientific information collected and communicated by the IPCC.

✓ Section 4: youth' feelings and thoughts about climate change

Participants were questioned about their feelings regarding climate change, how they imagine their future life to look like and what scientific questions about climate change they have.

✓ Section 5: how can IPCC help you?

This section was by far the longest one. It looked at what were the participants' expectations regarding IPCC, in terms of type of products but also of content. Subsection 1 focused on the participants' current use of IPCC products; subsection 2 looked at the participants' interest for specific topics; subsection 3 focused on the range of IPCC products and if the participants knew these, if they used them, if they were understandable and if they would have comments and recommendations; finally subsection 4 aimed at collecting ideas and suggestions on other type of material and means of communication the IPCC could develop, engaging young people. Participants could add something relevant they wanted the IPCC to know or give us their contact information if we needed more precise answers.

✓ Section 6: closing

We primary developed the questionnaire in English language, so that it could be as accessible as possible to all. We then received a request from a representative of an African youth organisation asking if we could create a French and a Portuguese version, since many of their members would feel more comfortable expressing themselves in those languages. Unfortunately, due to a lack of resources, a Portuguese version could not be created, but a French version was developed and circulated. Thus, two separate questionnaires were sent to the organisations. This whole process took about a week and a half and happened during the end of the organisation's identifying process.

Sending the questionnaire and analysis

The questionnaire was sent to all the organisations identified, and this over 2 weeks. We sent a reminder if the organisation didn't reply after a few days. Our email informed them about all the rules of procedure and kindly asked them to spread it among their youth members as well as other organisations they knew, which would be interested. Some organisations asked if they could post the links on their social media and others

mentioned sending them through their newsletter. Once they replied positively, we asked if they wanted their organisation to be acknowledged as a contributor in this report.

The survey was closed on 30 June and the data was downloaded to be analysed. We first cleared the data by isolating the answers from participants over 30 years old.

In total, 643 participants answered the questionnaires: 321 for the English version and 322 for the French one (see Annex II – Graphic 1). We decided to make a global analysis including all the answers and then to cluster by language to check how different or similar they were. Whereas English may not be the first language for a lot of participants who answered the English questionnaire, French is probably the first language for the majority of participants of the French questionnaire.

The data was stored and analysed using Excel. For quantitative answers, we calculated percentages and compared the French and the English version's percentages. As for the written answers, we sorted them into categories, negative-positive or themed.

In order to have a broader picture of the participants' geographical repartition, we used the WMO (World Meteorological Organization) classification⁴: participants were classified into 6 regions (Africa - Asia - South America - North America, Central America and Caribbean - South West Pacific - Europe).

Limits and possible bias to consider

Geographical imbalance

We succeeded in reaching participants from all over the world, in the five continents. Nevertheless, it is strongly imbalanced, as there are way more participants from the Europe region. Indeed, around 7 people out of 10 are living in Europe. France is the country where the most participants are from. It represents a bit more than 4 participants out of 10.

This huge imbalance might impact the results which are probably European oriented. European culture, state of knowledge, and climate events are probably taken into account by the majority of the participants at the expense of the other region's culture and climate. We need to be very cautious when this data is being used, and acknowledge the fact that it doesn't represent the global youth' position worldwide.

Age differences

We received answers from participants of all ages from 11 to 30. But again, there is a huge imbalance. The vast majority of the participants are more than 20 years old: it represents more than 7 people out of 10. The answers are not the same depending on the age of the respondents. The knowledge, experience, vocabulary and understanding vary according to the age. Thus, we need to be aware of this when using the questionnaire's results.

Moreover, we don't have any proof of what the participants answered. We couldn't control if people didn't lie about their age and thus, awareness about that is important.

Experience differences

We noticed that the answers were pretty different regarding the youth experience, especially if climate science is or was their field of studies. Indeed, we noticed that there are a few participants who mentioned studying climate change or working with or as a researcher. Their answers are very linked to their activity

⁴ https://contacts.wmo.int/all_members/

(especially when asked to write some questions toward a climate expert or when asked if they knew some IPCC material). We can imagine that this type of experience can represent a bias in all the collected answers, as it impacts the quality of the answers.

Geographical and cultural differences

As we reached people from a lot of different places, their answers were very probably impacted by the area they come from and their local reality. We noticed that with the questions asked to climate experts, where people were asking questions about their region or particular things, linked to where they live. For example, several people from Democratic Republic of Congo mentioned their forest and the impact climate change has on it. Some people mentioned rural and vulnerable communities. Others, in majority from Europe, asked questions about nuclear energy and a Norwegian youth asked about pumping oil from the ocean. A lot of people from Africa also mentioned the inclusion of Africa, in the IPCC or in the international sphere.

Furthermore, many participants who were from a developed country (notably from Switzerland, that was mentioned a lot) had projections that we ranked in the “neutral” category; indeed, they were quite optimistic about their country’s future, but also worried about what might happen in more vulnerable regions. Moreover, several Congolese participants praised their country’s situation and had positive projections for the future.

Nevertheless, since we know that the answers are geographically imbalanced, we need to be careful when a participant mentions a local reality.

Interests in climate issues

What stands out after the answers’ analysis is that these young persons are familiar with both the IPCC and climate change. They know a lot about the first and are interested in the second, and eager to learn more about it. That is shown by their investment in this questionnaire, their questions and concerns that are sometimes quite technical, for certain by their academic background, and for a vast majority of them by their affiliation to one or more youth organisations (that are mostly climate organisations). Thus, their answers and advice are those of a climate aware part of the population. This must be kept in mind when considering this survey’s results.

Participants

The first questions aimed to grasp the participants’ profile: their gender, their age, their nationality/ies and their country/ies of residence.

In terms of gender we can note a majority of female participants (55%) (see Annex II – Graphic 2).

Regarding the age of the respondents, these ranged from 11 to 30 years old with an overall average age of 22.6 years old (23.7 for the English survey and 21.8 for the French survey) (see Annex II – Graphic 3). We chose to take into account the few participants that were below 15 (in total, there were 7 of them, 4 among the English survey answers and 3 among the French survey ones).

In terms of citizenship (see Annex II – Graphic 4), a majority of the respondents were Europeans (answers from 24 different countries in Europe with a majority of French citizens). Citizens from the Africa were also well represented (from 20 different countries) whereas South America and South West Pacific were the least two represented regions.

The list of countries of residence (see Annex II – Graphic 5) was similar to the nationalities one, except that no participant lived in Azerbaijan, China, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Gabon, Hungary, Liechtenstein, Mauritania, Paraguay and Russia, and that one participant lived in Denmark.

In the end, even if Europeans represented a substantial part of the participants, we still received a lot of answers coming from all around the world.

The participants had also to indicate where they had accessed to the questionnaire. 7 options were available: via youth organisation - via their school - via a relative - via their professional activity - via the IPCC WGI TSU - via social media - other (they could complete this section). In “Other”, participants mentioned newsletters, previous colleagues, WhatsApp groups, University relations (group chat, professors, student or news), climate activists or organisations group chats, professional relatives and organisation platform. It appears that Youth organisations were the most efficient communication path (see Annex II – Graphic 6)

We also asked the participants if they were part or not of a youth/student/climate organisation/network and, if yes, to indicate which one. A majority of participants (57%) belonged to one or more youth organisations (see Annex II – Graphic 7). The most cited organisations were:

- ✓ the Catholic Youth Network for Environmental Sustainability in Africa (CYNESA),
- ✓ Fridays For Future (FFF) with different local groups,
- ✓ Generation Climate Europe,
- ✓ Global youth Biodiversity Network,
- ✓ Greenpeace,
- ✓ Pakistan Girl Guides Association (PGGA),
- ✓ Jeunes Ambassadeurs pour le Climat (JAC),
- ✓ Malaysian Youth Delegate,
- ✓ Wavemakers united,
- ✓ YOUNGO,
- ✓ Student Energy,
- ✓ Youth4climate,
- ✓ Youth and Environment Europe (YEE),
- ✓ World Association of Girl Guides and Girl Scouts (WAGGGS),
- ✓ UNICEF,
- ✓ School Strike for Climate, Press – Redd Barna Ungdom (PRESS-RBU),
- ✓ Save the children,
- ✓ Réseau Climate et Développement,
- ✓ Pour un réveil écologique,
- ✓ Association des Elèves et Etudiants Musulmans de Côte d'Ivoire (AEEMCI),
- ✓ Jeunes Volontaires pour l'Environnement (JVE),
- ✓ Italian climate Network, and Ghana Youth Environmental Movement.

Youth and the IPCC

Do young people know the IPCC?

The tendency is indisputable: participants of both questionnaires massively knew the IPCC (see Annex II – Graphic 8). This tells us more about our audience: they are people that were at least minimally aware of climate change issues.

The thing they most knew about the IPCC was that it prepares Assessments Reports about the state of scientific knowledge on climate change, its impacts and solutions to reduce climate change. The second thing was that it is the United Nation body for collecting and evaluating the science related to climate change. Youth were also pretty confident in the fact that IPCC reports are neutral and do not make political stands or

recommendations about climate change and its solutions. The majority of them also knew that the IPCC doesn't organise the COPs but gives scientific information to the participants about climate change. On the contrary, the facts they knew the least were that experts and authors who work on IPCC reports are not paid by the IPCC and that all the IPCC decisions are made by consensus. It is interesting to notice that there were no major differences between the English questionnaire's answers and the French ones on this question (see Annex II – Graphic 9).

Do young people trust the scientific information provided by the IPCC?

When asked the participants to rate their trust in the scientific information communicated by the IPCC, most of the youth gave a mark of 10 out of 10 (48,21%) and the vast majority gave more than a 7 out of 10 (85,85%) (see Annex II – graphic 10). Again, the results were quite similar between the English and the French versions.

We could calculate Net Promoter Score (NPS) of the answers. The NPS, which is the difference between the percentage of promoters (9 to 10) and the detractors (1 to 6), represents here the participant's degree of trust in the IPCC work reliability. The total NPS was 62, and the English survey and French survey ones were respectively 59 and 64. This means that there were a lot more promoters than detractors. Globally, participants had therefore faith in the reliability of the IPCC work.

Youth and climate

How do young people feel about climate change?

We first asked the youth how much they agreed with certain climate-related statements. 5 options to answer were proposed: *strongly agree* - *agree* - *neutral* - *disagree* - *strongly disagree*.

Participants globally disagreed with the positive statements: they do not feel listened to, nor confident or excited. On the contrary, they are anxious about the future, notably because a lot of them already suffer the effects of climate change (See Annex II – graphic 11)

This tendency was strengthened by their answers to the next question. Indeed, they could express their feelings regarding the current climate situation by writing down 3 adjectives to describe them. Both in the French (and English versions, the most used adjective was "*anxious*" ("*anxieux.se*"). In the English version, the word "*worried*" came second and the word "*angry*" came third, followed by negative adjectives such as "*powerless*" or "*frustrated*".

In the French version, the second most used adjective was "*impuissant.e*" (powerless). We then got "*inquiétant.é*" (worrying) et "*effrayant*" (scary). No positive adjectives were used more than twice.

Cloud of words that were cited

Most used words in the English survey / Most used words in the French survey

How do young people project themselves in the future relatively to climate change?

Participants were then asked to imagine their future life, from a climate point of view, in the region they live in. The answers of each survey were sorted in three categories, in order to make tendencies stand out: positive, neutral and negative projections. The neutral group brought together answers mixed between fear and hope.

In both surveys, more than 65% of answers were negative projections, about 23% of them were considered neutral and only 10% were positive (see Annex II - graphic 12).

The “negative” feelings

Among the negative answers, different tones were used: some participants remained factual in their projections, while others were marked by emotion. The main topics highlighted were:

- ✓ the increase in natural disasters' frequency
- ✓ the discrepancies of climate change's impacts
- ✓ the uncertain and hazardous nature of the future.

[when an area was specifically mentioned on a topic by one or more participants, it is written in parentheses with e.g. before]

A vast majority of participants forecast intense heatwaves and extremely high temperatures that might be “unbearable” (e.g. Bordeaux region): it was the topic that came back the most. A dry future was also predicted, with prolonged droughts (e.g. in Poland) and massive desertification (e.g. in the Iberian Peninsula). Similarly, participants imagined recurrent water scarcity and restrictions on drinkable water (e.g. in Perpignan, in the south of France). Floods were also one of the main topics mentioned by participants, as well as the multiplication of extreme weather events, such as storms, hailstorms and thunderstorms (e.g. La Réunion with cyclones). Seasons' disruption and the absence of a discernible weather pattern (e.g. in Guangzhou), rising of sea levels (e.g. in Bangladesh, Bretagne and Indonesia) and increasing of wildfires (e.g. in Southern Italy) were at the heart of youth's projections too. Participants were also preoccupied with the melting of ice caps (e.g. Pakistan glaciers melting) and disappearance of ski stations. There were finally lots of concerns about biodiversity loss, ecosystems' destabilisation and collapse, with species passing away (such as corals) and others appearing.

The quality of life was then seen as decreasing, with food scarcity and famines, health diseases and reduction of life expectancy, and the rise of cost living. More generally, many participants described their future as marked by social and political crises, such as migratory crises, conflicts around resources and discrepancies' increases, with the emergence of a “new poverty”.

Projections finally included worries about difficulties that agriculture might face (e.g. in rural zones in France), about pollution and the degradation of air quality, about salinisation of rivers and soils and about mosquitoes.

Negative and painful emotions also took up a lot of space in the youth's projections. If weariness and sadness were mentioned, it was fear that came back the most. Participants described themselves as scared of inaction, of a “worsening” situation and of a “terrible”, “uncertain” and “unstable” future. “Our future life is in danger” declared a participant. They were afraid of the next generation's future, to such an extent that some of them considered not having children. A participant talked about mental and psychological disorders. The fascism rise (e.g. in Switzerland and Sweden) that democracies might not resist to, was also a concern: several participants expressed their fear of a racist, segregated and divided society. Projections were marked by anxiety about social crises and chaos to come and about the human species' vulnerability before natural disasters. The unfairness of climate change impacts was emphasised as well: developed countries, that contributed the most to climate change, will be the ones to suffer the less its effects.

Many participants also placed death at the crux of their projection. Some of them mentioned their own death, declaring that their health was already deteriorating, that they might die because of a natural disaster, and that life might one day become survival. Others focused on other people's death, by predicting the ones of vulnerable groups, such as migrants in the Mediterranean Sea or deaths in Egypt because of high temperatures.

Finally, several answers had a defeatist tone: one participant declared they had no hope for the government's action, and another that even if everybody became completely aware of climate change issues, it will never be a priority for people.

It was also interesting to note a few expressions used by youth: *“reduce the environment to ashes”*; *“global boiling”*; *“from books to reality, a nightmare in process”*; *“we may no longer be on this earth”*.

The “positive” feelings

Positive answers consisted of hopes for the future, beliefs in improvements, optimism and more simply positive feelings (several participants used terms such as *“joy”*, *“bright”*, *“good”*, *“great”* to depict their future life). Most of the optimistic projections described their trust in people’s ability to act together to *“make the world better”*. They imagined a collective engagement to take actions on climate issues, leading to an environmentally-friendly mutual aid society.

A couple of them particularly highlighted the youth’s power, considering *“us strong enough to protect the environment”* and expressing their will to create a better future for the next generations. A participant highlighted their belief in individual actions. Several of them imagined themselves finding solutions, raising awareness and polarising climate change issues by joining an organisation or the political sphere.

For other participants, humanity could head with a values’ transformation towards a post-growth ideal society; this could be a new way of living together centred on well-being, sustainable production, honest relationships and with more direct democracy.

A number of them were also optimistic regarding their future life, as they were reassured by people’s and notably organisations’ current investment and work to solve climate change issues (the city of Bouaké was specifically mentioned).

Hopes in overcoming challenges and finding solutions (to for instance manage extreme events and avoid scarcity) took a lot of space as well in youth positive projections. Participants described their future as carbon neutral, thanks to nature-based solutions, renewable energies, urban farming, public transport, company resettlement, green cities and new habits that have less impacts on climate change. One participant depicted a future of consensus at intergovernmental levels.

Finally, a couple of participants imagine the future of a specific country/region. Congo was described multiple times as a solution country, as lungs and its future life was qualified as *“peaceful”*. Kenya and more generally East Africa were depicted as references in terms of climate resilience and sustainable living, thanks to their green innovations and infrastructures (such as their flood management system, their sustainable farming, drought-resistant crops...). A participant also described a future life in Switzerland as enjoyable, since they believed the country not to be strongly affected and to have financial resources to adapt.

The “neutral” group

The neutral group is quite heterogeneous; some participants described their own individual life, while others imagined climate change consequences on a global scale.

Several participants remained completely factual in their projections; they described impassively how their future life will be marked by climate change effects, such as extreme heat and economic challenges.

A few of them declared that adaptation was needed; one participant answered for instance *“Reset. Change. Adaptation.”*

Others considered moving, especially out of cities or to the mountains. A couple of them mentioned Brittany as a potential place of residence, a possibility strengthened by the answer of a Breton participant, who spoke very highly of the region and planned to stay on. A participant declared that he was considering autarky; several participants also depicted a life with restrictions, “*a life under duress*”.

Many participants, who lived in a developed country or in a “*safe place*”, compared their country’s future situation to other countries’ (e.g. mostly Switzerland, and Norway). Some of them said they won’t be impacted by climate change effects, thanks to their country’s wealth, but that they still worry about potential social injustices that could be caused in the world. Others imagined their situation to be difficult with, for instance, water shortages or rising prices, but that it will be liveable, compared to other regions. Thus, many of them declared they expected migrants to come to their country. That is why other participants described a future with natural disasters of course, but above all with mutual aid.

There were numerous participants that invoked the concept of change in their projections. They talked about a different life, that was not how they thought it would be; they depicted a lifestyle that would be at odds with the current one (e.g. a life of sobriety with redesigned uses or another life rhythm where people would sleep during the day and live during the night).

Lots of answers were mixed and vague about the future, viewing it as hard but possible, as impacted but liveable, as alright but dangerous and with no huge changes on the personal scale. This type of answer was mostly made by participants that declared being well-off.

There was also a lot of uncertainty in the answers. A couple of participants considered different scenarios, and their consequences. For instance, a young person imagined a situation in which net-zero had been reached by society, and another in which not (e.g. In Rwanda). A participant declared that their life in the next 10 years would be hard but liveable, and that beyond that, it was uncertain but probably worse. For another participant, the future would depend on countries’ decisions. Finally, many young people didn’t manage to look at the future.

What questions do young people have relatively to climate change?

We noticed that the questions youth were interested in could be classified into several categories.

Actions to be taken to help mitigate climate change?

In this category, there are also different types of questions. The first ones are about governments’ inaction and how to make it change. It concerns a great number of questions. Some are more specific and ask how to ensure the government follows agreements or laws. Others are about politics, democracy and consensus.

A lot are also concerning individual actions: they are mentioning the effectiveness of individual actions and asking about concrete ideas and actions.

Then, there are a lot of questions about actions to be taken to raise awareness whether how to do it or about its effectiveness.

Moreover, quite a few people asked about policies to be taken in order to mitigate climate change. Others are questioning international negotiations and laws and their effectiveness.

Finally, the youth are also wondering about actions to be taken without too big of an impact on the economy or actions to be taken by companies and industries or as a society.

Science facts

There were lots of questions about the science facts, in majority including tipping points and irreversibility of climate change. Scenarios, models and projections are also a big topic for questions as well as local and regional realities. Youth are wondering what is going to happen, where and if it is still stoppable.

Some questions were about the factors of climate change and about its impacts (greenhouse gas and ozone have been mentioned a couple of times).

Some questions were about the oceans (AMOC) and water scarcity, and others about biodiversity. Youth also had questions about misinformation and about the methods used to collect all the scientific knowledge or build projections and models, as well as uncertainties scientists have.

New technologies

A lot of young people are wondering if geoengineering is reliable and if there are technological innovations that could help mitigate climate change. There were also several questions about cars and energy (fossil fuels, renewable and nuclear energy).

What solutions?

Another big question is about what solutions are there to tackle or to adapt to climate change. We received a lot of vague questions like *“What is the solution?”*.

Other topics

Then, there are quite a few questions about the youth themselves, their job career, their own future, children or the impact of their activism.

The youth are also very interested in climate justice and inequalities, whether it is between continents or countries or even communities. They are wondering how the climate crisis affects those inequalities or how to involve or take into account the most vulnerable people.

Participants also had a lot of questions toward the scientist as a person, mainly about how they manage their feelings, how they engage people, if they have hope or how do they find their energy.

How can the IPCC help youth?

How useful are the IPCC actions/activities to you?

See Annex II – Graphic 13

Participants had to rate (from 0 to 10) how much the IPCC and its activities help them for their different activities of knowledge. If the answers' average was/is 7,5 out of ten, the NPS are way lower than the trust NPS. Indeed, the total NPS is 8, the English survey one 16 and the French survey one 1. This means that there were almost as many promoters as detractors; the IPCC helped as many people as it did not.

Interest in different topics

Participants had to rank 6 topics, from the most interesting to the least interesting.

Therefore, the main concerns of participants were global concerns (How to reduce climate change everywhere and global impacts and effects of climate change). How we can estimate the quantity of greenhouse gas emissions and how to remove greenhouse gases from the atmosphere (from the air) was

the very last to arrive in both questionnaires; participants cared less about a very specific and technical topic like this one (see Annex I – Graphic 14)

What do youth want to learn more about?

Participants had then to answer the following questions: Is there anything you wish you had **more scientific knowledge** about? Something you want to **know more about**? Which **major question(s)** would you expect the **next IPCC reports** to address?

After some answers (48) that concerned directly the IPCC work and the workings of climate change were put aside, the rest of them were sorted into two categories:

- ✓ answers related to IPCC work and climate change ongoing studies
- ✓ answers related to impacts of climate change (143)
- ✓ answers related to solutions and actions to take (242)

IPCC work and ongoing studies

A lot of participants were interested in learning more about climate change in general. Some of them asked questions about its causes (e.g. climate effects of different materials such as clothing and furniture, and biochemistry of the effects of climate change). They were also curious about the evolution of climate change, and notably about models and their potential popularisation. They asked for climate forecasts, projections of future climate scenarios per region and precisions on how these scenarios are calculated and projections for global temperature-rise and sea level-rise.

Participants also had specific questions, about tipping points, abrupt changes in weather patterns and atmospheric science and protection of the ozone layer. One participant asked for the types of climates, and another asked what the difference between climate change and global warming was. Finally, a participant asked whether or not open questions in the climate change field remained.

Participants also requested explanations on the IPCC workings. A couple of them advised the IPCC to be more positive in their work but others encouraged them not to be afraid of being scaremongering.

Information related to impacts of climate change

Oceans were one of the topics that came back the most; participants had questions about the potential interrelation between climate change and oceans, and notably about carbon capture in the ocean. Global sea level rise, ocean's temperatures and consequences on coral reefs, and the Gulfstream were recurrent themes. They asked the IPCC to address impacts of human activities and of plastic and chemical pollution on the marine ecosystems. Finally, ocean deoxygenation and massive evaporation of ocean's waters were mentioned.

Long term effects of climate change on biodiversity and ecosystems were asked to be addressed. The future of specific key species was questioned, as well as the potential animal migrations due to climate change. Participants also asked why biodiversity was so important for the ecological balance, and why would its collapse be such a danger for humans. A couple of them also required the IPCC to study specifically the Forest's situation and future.

Participants also wished to have more knowledge about climate change impacts on health, in particular on the human body, on well-being and on mental health. Calculation of deaths caused by climate change was required a lot. A participant wondered about the potential adaptations of health infrastructures in order to cope with increased health damages due to climate change. Another specifically asked what might be the consequences of climate change on the distribution and incidence of vector-borne diseases like malaria, dengue and Lyme disease.

Political, social and economic effects of climate change were as well at the crux of participants' concerns. They first asked about impacts of climate change on politics, and about possible conflicts and political instability it might induce. The link between governments, living conditions and environmental impacts was then mentioned, as well as the ways for democracy to face a climate crisis. There were also lots of questions about social impacts of climate change, in particular about cultural loss and inequalities of impact between different groups (such as gender, ethnic or economic groups). The fundamental rights jeopardised by global warming were asked to be highlighted. Participants also required the IPCC to address the link between climate change and neo-colonialism, as well as the economic dimension of it.

Then came questioning about regional and local impacts. Participants asked how and why climate change impacts differently each region and especially vulnerable areas. The contrast of effects in the Global North and the Global South was mentioned a lot. Climate change impacts on small islands developing states and on mountains were required. Finally, many participants asked for forecasts and explanations of climate change consequences in a specific place (Germany, Austria, Spain, Djibouti, Congo...).

Participants' will to know more about the climate crisis and other crises was also noticeable. They had questions about the current climate crisis and about climate transition risks. They also asked for the IPCC to address linkages to other crises, such as water, food and energy scarcities, demographic crises and migration crises.

They wished to have more knowledge on greenhouse gas as well, notably on their impacts on the environment, their relation with climate change, on the ways one can quantify them and eliminate them from the atmosphere. Specific questions were asked, like methodologies to estimate GHG emissions from degradation in savannas (Brazilian Cerrado) and an estimation of the imported emissions of Norway.

Participants were also curious about the link between global commerce chain and climate change, and especially about the companies' role in it. They asked who the main polluters were, what the environmental impacts of big firms, superprofits and oil companies were, whether it is feasible to transform the actions of large responsible corporations, and how to do it.

Finally, participants had questions on very specific topics: impacts of climate change on the atmospheric circulation (e.g. Hadley cell rising), potential environmental impacts of quantum computing, effects of changing precipitation patterns on agriculture, water resources and biodiversity, global warming-related storms and hurricanes formation (e.g. about El Nino and La Nina) and links between climate change and AI.

Information related to solutions / actions to take

A lot of topics required by participants were related to a climate resilient economy. They indeed wanted to know more about economic policies, in particular about those necessary to a fair ecological transition. Many of them wondered about the cost distribution of such a transition. Conflicts of interest between stakeholders linked to individual costs were also at the heart of participants' concerns; when one wished to learn more about the economic benefits of climate actions (especially of renewable energies), another asked how to manage to reduce GHG when it is not a lucrative enough option for big companies. Themes such as growth, degrowth, stagnation, capitalism, non-capitalist scenarios and alternative lifestyles (such as sobriety) came back a lot. Participants also requested that the IPCC addresses subjects as carbon market, climate finance and climate change fundings. Finally, they asked questions about concrete actions companies can do, agriculture's resilience and globalisation's limits.

Participants also had a lot of questions concerning national and international governance. Several participants wanted the IPCC to explain how climate change can be tackled on a global scale and how to act

as a society. There were many questions on the active and concrete actions one country can take, on what the most effective policy instruments were, and what should be a government's priorities in terms of climate change. What was also noticeable was the participants' will to understand the importance of intergovernmental discussions and agreements, such as Climate Assessment and COP. Questions related to governments' lack of action came back a lot as well: how can one explain it? How to constrain even countries with strong worldwide influence to act? How could this inaction be punished?

Finally, participants wondered about the climate change-related relations between the Global North and the Global South; they brought up topics such as responsibility, current impacts of one's actions on the other and the help needed by developing countries.

Measures to overcome climate change challenges and their efficiency were also requested to be addressed. Participants indeed had a lot of questions about mitigation and adaptation measures; they often wondered which strategies were the most useful and what their socioeconomic implications would be. Their concerns were also related to the effectiveness of current efforts, notably to the feasibility of limiting global warming to 1.5°C.

More specifically, participants wanted the IPCC to explore geoengineering and technologies. They wished to learn more about mitigation and adaptation technologies and about benefits, effectiveness but also risks of geoengineering. A participant particularly wanted to understand how technological innovations confront institutions. Besides, many questions concerned carbon capture and storage (CCS) and other active strategies to remove harmful agents from the environment. Participants had then specific questions, about nuclear and renewable energies, about the application of the latter in rural settings, about "green" electricity storage, about green hydrogen and finally about rare metals in batteries.

Then came the topic of individual and youth actions. To begin with, they wondered how to involve citizens and how everyone can contribute. There were also several questions about youth's responsibility and what they could do, about individual actions one can take in one's daily life and especially about the true impact of these kinds of actions. For instance, one participant asked about the effects of reducing meat consumption.

Several participants also wished for a social and societal approach of climate change to be included in the IPCC work. Firstly, a couple of questions were about "*climate psychology*": how to influence behaviours, how people are likely to react to changes that are standing out, what are the links between climate change and people's well-being and anxiety, why are some people paralysed and unable to act.... Participants also asked for more social science and even for philosophy in order to explain how societies can change, to study the acceptability of politics and to analyse the question of responsibility (both individual and collective). Among the questions, there were also the role of media and their impact through the general public perceptions and political debate. A participant requested a sociological approach, to help imagining a better future. Finally, an historical analysis of current society's development was asked.

Nature based solutions and urban adaptation constituted another category of questions. Participants were indeed curious about the relation between cities and climate change; they wondered about the benefits of urban adaptation, about how to improve the resilience and climate-friendly nature of cities, about the effects of urban heat islands and about the most ecological way to insulate houses. They also had questions about benefits, costs and potential damages of nature-based solutions, such as wind farms and solar panels. Finally, participants asked about heat conservation in soils, about hydropower and reduction of GHG and about agriculture's impacts according to soil size and surficial biomass.

Local solutions were a quite regular topic in the answers; several participants asked for the best mitigation and adaptation strategies for a specific region (Caribbean, Southeast Asia, arid regions like Djibouti and rural

regions in developing countries). One participant asked how to bridge academic ecological knowledge and local ecological knowledge.

Participants also asked for concrete recommendations to protect worldwide biodiversity, to cleanse the environment, to restore damaged ecosystems and to help fauna and flora species that are endangered by climate change.

They also wished the IPCC to address climate justice, notably by answering the following questions: How to ensure equity and justice in climate action? How to face climate change challenges in a socially just way? Who is considered to be vulnerable from legal and policy perspectives?

A few questions were about trash management, notably about the reduction of the amount of plastic, about waste management that would be safer for the planet and about the links between garbage quantity and overproduction.

Participants were curious as well about jobs (“green” jobs created by an ecological transition and, on the contrary, environmentally harmful activities in order to raise awareness), education (climatology course in schools) and communication (participants wanted to know how to explain climate change and how to answer fake news, how to fight climate disinformation).

Finally, participants had very specific questions about positive feedback loops, climate feedbacks, land expropriation, land take, biomimicry and car pollution.

Youth and the IPCC material

The aim was to study the proximity of youth to the IPCC material; we wanted to understand to what extent they knew it, they understood it and how they thought it could be improved.

In this section, the term “IPCC material” stands for a grouping of available products as follows:

- ✓ the Summary for Policymakers (SPM)

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_SYR_SPM.pdf

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_WGI_SPM.pdf

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_WGII_SummaryForPolicymakers.pdf

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_WGIII_SummaryForPolicymakers.pdf

- ✓ the Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)

<https://www.ipcc.ch/help/frequently-asked-questions/>

- ✓ the fact sheets

<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/resources/factsheets/>

<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/about/factsheets/>

<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/resources/factsheets/>

- ✓ the interactive atlas

<https://interactive-atlas.ipcc.ch/>

- ✓ the Summary for all

<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/resources/summary-for-all/>

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/downloads/outreach/IPCC_AR6_WGII_SummaryForAll_Adaptation.pdf

- ✓ the report video

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SDRxfuEvgGg>

Knowledge of available IPCC material

See Annex II – Graphic 15

Participants were firstly asked whether or not they knew about the existing IPCC material.

In both questionnaires, the SPM was the document that was the most known by the participants, followed by the Summary for all. The least known documents were the report video and the interactive Atlas.

To notice that the French survey participants knew less about the IPCC material than the English survey ones.

Clarity of the IPCC material

Participants then got asked whether they found the material easy to understand or not. There was no choice/answer suggested.

The English survey received 170 answers that were taken into account and the French survey 129. In order to bring tendencies out, we clustered the answers into 4 categories:

- ✓ (1) Yes, everything is easy to understand
- ✓ (2) None of it is
- ✓ (3) It depends on the document
- ✓ (4) Yes because of an exterior factor

See Annex II – Graphic 16

Among both the French and English answers, the main reasons raised in order to explain a failure to understand the IPCC material were the complexity and the technicity of the documents. The target audience was not the general public (i.e people with no scientific knowledge). This was strengthened by the answers part of cluster (4). In fact, almost all of these answers were of the following form: *Yes I understand everything, but I have a [scientific formation/background/interest]*. Many among the participants that were sorted in this category explicitly worried about the understandable nature of the material for people with no/few scientific knowledge.

Among the participants who replied positively regarding one or more specific documents, the SPM was the document that was judged the easiest to understand. However, among the participants who replied negatively regarding one or more specific documents, the SPM was judged difficult to understand, followed by the Summary for all (and the Atlas).

In the end, the summaries were both the easier and the most difficult to understand. One hypothesis that could explain this phenomenon is that the summaries are the most read IPCC documents; indeed, participants talked about the documents they had read.

Suggestions from participants on the IPCC material

Participants had then to answer the following question: Do you have any **suggestions** to make on these documents? Please indicate which document you are talking about. It was an open question, without any choice/answer suggested.

The English survey got 73 answers we could take into account, and the French one got 42 of them. Some suggestions were general in scope, while others concerned one specific document.

The problem that was the most raised in both questionnaires was the complexity of the language used in each document. *“The info provided is often hard to digest and not for general use” (English survey)*. As emphasised in this answer, participants reproached the IPCC material for their convoluted and specialised

scientific writing, because it was not understandable for the general public, for people with no scientific background or knowledge on the subject.

Among the suggestions to make the IPC material easier to understand, the most cited one was to either simplify directly the documents (e.g. with shorter and clearer sentences), or to create simpler versions of them. Participants also suggested to include popularised content in each section, to indicate the background knowledge required to understand the material and to produce concise summaries and key takeaways for each chapter.

The visual aspect of all the documents could also be improved: to ease the reading and the understanding, the IPCC could add infographics and schemas to assist complex data, include simpler graphics and even incorporate expert quotes or fun visuals. Versions for children of the documents were even suggested. The estheticism of the Facts sheets was notably praised.

According to the participants, the material could also be more accessible and prompt more people to fight for climate by including practical recommendations (notably of actions one can take at the individual scale) and concrete examples (of climate change impacts for instance).

Another request that came back a lot, especially in the English survey, was the translation of the IPCC material into as many languages as possible, in order to reach as many people as possible.

Participants of both questionnaires also advised the IPCC to improve its communication around its material (a lot of them did not know about all the available material before this survey). They consider the IPCC work not known enough of the general public. To fix this, some of them suggested asking governments and organisations to broadcast the documents (notably the summaries) in schools and companies, and even to present it on TV. Besides, the most recurrent suggestion to enhance the popularisation of the IPCC work and role was to get (more) involved on social media (instagram, tiktok...), with short videos (less than 1 minute). *“Most young people now consume video rather than written content. The only video you offer is too conventional (boring) and looks like a classic TV commercial, even though young people don't watch TV anymore. You should produce more videos, long and short, and take inspiration from YouTube or TikTok popular formats” (English survey).*

The last suggestion to reach a broader public concerned the IPCC material content. Some participants indeed requested the inclusion of underrepresented groups' perspective, notably how they are impacted by climate change. Among these groups, people with low-income, disabilities or belonging to ethnic minorities were mentioned, but the category which was the most referred to was young people. The solution proposed was then to include youth's voices in the different materials by adding testimonies, and by spotting a light on what they think and how they act for the climate.

General remarks about the IPCC materials content were made as well: more clarity on the low impact of individual actions (because this is the prism used in school to teach the subject), a stronger emphasis on the governments' silence and its effects, a section indicating which economic solutions are viable, and finally more aspects such as the impacts on ecosystems should be included in the graphs.

Participants gave as well more specific advice on each document.

Summary for Policymakers

Some suggested simplifying the language in this document in particular, others to share it better in the political sphere. In the previous question, one participant described it as *“hard to digest”* for people with no scientific background. Some participants noted that the SPM did not really popularise climate physics.

It was also requested:

- ✓ to include explicit measures and examples of how to implement these measures in different regions
- ✓ to integrate statistic data in a more systematic way
- ✓ to “Clarify what the "Earth system" is, and that climate is only one of its parameters for controlling its habitability for our civilization and species”
- ✓ that the modification of the SPM should be exclusively reserved to scientists.

Summary for all

The visual aspect of this document came back a few times in the suggestions: according to the participants, it could be improved by diagrams, schemas and graphics. Some of them also suggested to broadcast it better.

Factsheets

A simplified version with less scientific language was suggested. Designs could also be improved by being more eye-catching according to some participants, so that people are more likely to share and understand them. One suggestion was the addition of renewable energy and energy storage fact sheets.

The video

As one can see on the quote above⁵, the video’s format was criticised, all the more so since another participant suggested that a more hopeful tone could be used, in order not to discourage people from acting.

The interactive atlas:

The interactive atlas is considered difficult to use by participants. More guidance and indications were requested, as well as short explanation texts. One of them requested links to the scientific papers used so they can go into the subject in depth. Another participant suggested the mesh of the atlas to be finer in order to visualise climate change’s impacts on national or regional scale.

FAQs - the IPCC website

A participant asked for a website that would be dedicated to communicating IPCC work to a non-scientific audience, with simple language. According to them, *“the IPCC website as it stands is not suitable for this”*.

Suggestions on communication

Participants could then suggest material they considered that could help the IPCC to engage young people. All the answers were sorted in different types of documents.

One suggestion stood out from the crowd: social media. Participants of both questionnaires massively estimated that social media is the best way for the IPCC to reach youth: more than half of the answers were about social media. According to them, the IPCC has to make social networks one of its main communication sources; it would enable the IPCC to widen its audience by reaching communities that had no knowledge of it, especially young people, considering that social media is their principal information source.

The Instagram account of the IPCC was judged too conventional, too institutional and ill-adapted to social media workings and especially to a young audience.

⁵ “Most young people now consume video rather than written content. The only video you offer is too conventional (boring) and looks like a classic TV commercial, even though young people don’t watch TV anymore. You should produce more videos, long and short, and take inspiration from YouTube or TikTok popular formats” (English survey).

Participants' suggestions on how to broadcast the IPCC work on social media were plentiful. Among them, the short videos format that is suitable for Instagram or Tiktok came back the most. Videos were considered as an adequate tool to popularise and to decode climate change related subjects/causes and impacts, to explain mitigation and adaptation and to highlight the key ideas of the actions one can take. One participant suggested short videos about the greenhouse effect or about the radiative effects of aerosols for instance. Another one quoted as a quality reference the YouTube videos of the French journal *Le Monde*.

Many participants of both questionnaires also judged partnerships on social media the better way to reach youth nowadays. The IPCC could cooperate with either popular organisations or influencers, people who already have a young audience on these platforms. Hugo Décrypte was quoted twice for instance. These content creators, whom youth identify with, could help engage young people. One participant even suggested creating a team of Youtubers.

Participants advised as well the IPCC to produce short articles about climate change related subjects and synthesis of its work with data and key ideas that can be posted on social media. The fact sheets were quoted several times as suitable for this format. As imagery is nowadays one of the essential aspects of communication, many participants suggested posting infographics, schemas, mind maps or even comics. The last social media format that was suggested by participants was interactive content, via stories for instance, that exchanges with the audience and involves young people. Some participants also pointed out that an IPCC presence on social media could help to fight disinformation and misinformation.

In order to widen the audience and capture the youth's attention without necessarily using social media, participants advised the IPCC to produce videos, in the broad sense of the word. Indeed, young people today tend to read less; a participant even talked about a "*civilisation of oral tradition*". Some participants suggested presenting the IPCC materials and popularising the reports in videos. Others advised to diversify the videos' length, in order to have both short formats that would be regularly published and longer ones to study themes in depth.

Production of documentaries, series and films were also suggested several times (the streaming platform Netflix was quoted twice). They could be about the climate change impacts, solutions and international negotiations or even about the youth's engagement, with testimonies for instance. Video interviews with authors and experts were also required. Finally, participants in both questionnaires advised the IPCC to create educational videos that explain key ideas of climate change and the actions youth can take.

In order to help visual learners, infographics, pictures and maps were suggested. The Sustainable Development Goals of 2015 were used as a reference. Participants also recommended occupying the advertising space, with stickers, flyers, posters and ads with IPCC work and figures. A participant even proposed an illustrated digital campaign.

Another means of communication recommended by the participants was the organisation of events aimed at youth. To get to young people, conferences and seminars, online or not, where they could ask their questions were one of the main suggestions. The school sector also appeared as ideal for communication with young people. Participants suggested presentations of the IPCC work in class, polls and questionnaires in schools, and even the presence of IPCC representatives in high schools. Activities as the Climate Fresk (<https://fresqueduclimat.org/#>) came back a lot in the answers, as well as missions of public interest for the environment. On another scale, some participants also advocated the youth involvement in the IPCC work itself, for instance by soliciting them during the report's writing process, by holding COP with youth and by creating IPCC youth ambassadors.

Participants had some website and app suggestions for the IPCC to make information more accessible and engaging for young people. They advocated for instance the creation of an app on smartphones that would be devoted to the broadcasting of IPCC findings. Other participants raised the idea of an interactive website where the climate change impacts could be visible. The creation of an online forum, where people could ask questions to experts and exchange about their experience of climate change also came back a lot. Participants required a newsletter as well, and one asked for a monthly blog.

Since many young people are students, participants advised the IPCC to use school as a way to communicate with youth by producing teaching materials. Summaries for students were suggested, as well as the introduction of the IPCC work into curriculums. Teachers could have access to course material, such as summaries for students or textbooks about climate change, and to presentation slides about the most central findings of the IPCC. Some participants specifically recommended classes on the data of each IPCC report, climate solution-oriented workshops and mentorship programs offered by the IPCC. The goal would be to raise youth's awareness in educational surroundings and to empower them to contribute to climate change discussions and solutions. The International Primary Curriculum (IPC) was quoted as an example of organisation the IPCC could collaborate with in order to produce interactive learning materials on climate change.

Training courses (online or not) open to all were also required; at least two participants asked for a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course)..

Participants even considered that the IPCC should reach young people and especially children by investing in playful materials. Comics were the type of document that came back the most. *Le monde sans fin* from Jean-Marc Jancovici was quoted twice, *Algues vertes* from Inès Léraud once. Participants also suggested the development by the IPCC of games and especially video games, where for instance the player takes decisions for the entire planet, and the consequences follow. Finally, interactive materials, such as quizzes, exercises and riddles were proposed.

A participant even proposed the development of novels that would combine scientific knowledge and fun content.

Suggestions also included the production by the IPCC of accessible literature. Participants asked for informative books, surveys and articles in news and magazines with climate change related content. Guide books that provide concrete advice on individual actions to reduce carbon footprint were suggested as well.

Fact sheets were praised a lot among the answers: they were considered a good introduction to the IPCC for young people. In general, participants suggested syntheses with key ideas, data and arguments to understand climate change and to be able to discuss it. These index cards could contain IPCC important conclusions summaries, policies toolkits (i.e. what have been the most efficient policies and measures so far and which have most potentials) and suggestions for youth actions.

A couple of participants also asked for syntheses with different levels of understanding: accessible to all, basic scientific knowledge required, solid scientific background needed...

On top of that, participants advocated the creation of podcasts (for example in which every episode is devoted to one section of the report), in order to reach young people for whom long scientific papers could act as a deterrent.

Among the answers received, some could not be sorted in a specific category. A couple of participants praised this questionnaire, others called for industrial action and petitions, and some of them asked for a

specific report on young people, for a toolkit for youth about adaptation and leadership and for sign language during IPCC conferences.

In the end, many answers listed various materials and communication styles. Their advice was to diversify the IPCC communication in order to reach young people as much as possible.

Conclusion

In light of the participants' answers, notably those concerning topics they would like the IPCC to study, an element is blindingly obvious: they ask for content that is already included in the IPCC Reports, leading us to the following suggestion: should the IPCC improve and work on its communication about its role, its work and its available material? To do so, we first recommend investing more on social media, on audio-visual media and on teaching materials, since these are the main information sources for young people. In order to make the IPCC work more approachable, we advise to produce more intuitive visuals (notably on the IPCC website) and above all, to develop documents that are easier to understand. If this type of material could not be made by the IPCC, we would recommend to support more organisations which create accessible and popularised documents, and to recognise them in order to promote their actions. Thus, we support the IPCC on the efforts that are made to translate the materials into several languages and we encourage it to work on even more languages in order to offer a translation to a larger number of people (including the youth).

The participants of this questionnaire are young people that are interested in climate change and aware of its issues. But, most importantly, they represent an anxious and worried youth, who requests both explication and implication. We suggest to the IPCC to try to explain some governments' lack of action, as it is a source of both frustration and incomprehension for young people, and to produce more precise scenarios about specific regions, as their anxiety also comes from uncertainty. If these young people are anxious, they are however not giving up: they want to act. That is why we recommend the IPCC to communicate about the potential role that youth may play in the fight against climate change, and even to involve them in the IPCC work process.

Finally, since the participants were already familiar with climate change issues, we think that it would be interesting for the IPCC to conduct such a survey again, but this time with a broader audience that would be less climate aware. This would aim to determine the links of the general public with the IPCC and climate change, and to raise its awareness.

Annexes

Annex I – Survey

Youth and climate change

Prepared by the IPCC Working Group I Technical Support Unit

This form is for the youth and climate change community.
IPCC stands for Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change and it is an international group of climate experts who are evaluating the science related to climate change.

* Obligatoire

Youth and climate change form

Welcome to the Youth and Climate Change survey!

Young people are important stakeholders for the IPCC, and we would love to learn more about **your feelings and the questions you have** about climate change but also understand what you think of the IPCC and how the IPCC reports help you or can help you.

As we are starting the seventh assessment cycle, our main report will be themed and designed at the end of the year, and we are collecting ideas and themes that would interest the youth.

If you don't know what the IPCC is, no problem, **you can still participate!**

This form consists of 6 sections and has 24 questions in total. It should take you a **up to 30 minutes** to complete this form.

This is a unique opportunity for us to hear from you and will be an amazing resource.

The form is in **English**. If you are not comfortable using this language, feel free to use an **online translator**. You can answer the open questions (questions where you need to write the answer) using **your own language** but please **specify** which language it is just **before** writing your response at the beginning of your answer.

The form is anonymous and will **close on June 30th**. Data analysis will be run only by the IPCC Working Group I (WGI) Technical Support Unit (TSU).

Thank you very much in advance for your responses.

Who are you?

This section is for us to get to know you. This survey is anonymous, and all the collected data will remain private.

1. How old are you? *

2. What is your gender? *

- Female
- Male
- Other
- Prefer not to say

3. What is your **nationality(ies)**? *

4. What is your country of **residence**? *

5. Where did you find the link to this survey? *

- Via youth organization
- Via my school
- A relative (friend, family) forwarded to me
- Via my professional activity
- The IPCC WGI TSU forwarded to me
- I found it on social media
- Autre

6. Are you part of a youth/student/climate organization/network? *

- Yes
- No

7. If yes, please indicate which one:

8. Have you heard about the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) <https://www.ipcc.ch/> ?

*

Yes

No

Get to know the IPCC

We want to acknowledge what you know about the IPCC. It is okay if you are not sure about your answers!

9. Please tell us if you **knew** those information *

I already knew that

I knew it

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) is the **United Nations** body for collecting and evaluating the **science related to climate change**.

The IPCC is an **intergovernmental** organization and has **195 Member countries**.

All the IPCC decisions are made by **consensus** (all the member countries need to agree).

The IPCC prepares **Assessment Reports** (scientific document) about the **state of scientific knowledge** on climate change, its **impacts** and **solutions** to reduce climate change.

The IPCC **does not** conduct its own **research**. Experts and authors work to summarize what is known about climate

about climate change.

Experts and **authors** who work on IPCC reports are not paid by the IPCC.

IPCC experts and authors are from all over the world and there is a **geographical balance**, a **gender equality** and a **diversity** regarding previous experience and expertise.

IPCC reports are **neutral** and **do not** make **political stands** or **recommendations** about climate change and its solutions.

The IPCC **does not organize the COPs** (Conference of the Parties, it is an annual meeting about climate change, with governments from all over the world) but gives **scientific information** to the participants about climate change.

10. Do you **trust** the **scientific information** collected and communicated by the IPCC? *

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Not at all

Yes, absolutely

Your feelings and thoughts about climate change

The following questions are about how you feel.

11. Complete the following affirmations with what you think suits you best. *

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither
I am not worried at all about what my future will look like because of climate change. I feel confident about the future.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Thinking about climate change impacts me emotionally/ makes me anxious	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel powerless in the face of climate change	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel listened by the government/ the international organizations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think I know enough about climate change and the science behind it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel excited by all the opportunities that the climate crisis will offer.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I already experience the effects of climate change in my region.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12. Can you give us **3 adjectives** that describe **your feeling** when you think of the **current climate situation**? *

13. How do you imagine **your future life** to be, from a climate point of view, in the region you live in? *

14. If you had climate experts in front of you, **what questions** about the climate would you ask them, and why? *

How can the IPCC help you?

The IPCC is currently working on the **seventh evaluation cycle** and is willing to get to know the **youth's needs**. We would like you to tell us what **you expect** from the IPCC and what could **help you**, as a young climate conscious person.

15. If you knew the IPCC before answering this survey, would you say that the IPCC's actions (reports, workshops and expert meetings information, communications, press release...) **help you** in your different activities or for your general knowledge?

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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Absolutely not

Yes, definitely

16. Which topics are you the **most interested in?** (upwards indicates greater interest and downwards less interest) *

The impacts of climate change on my region/ city

The science on past, present, and future climate change

How we can estimate the quantity of greenhouse gas emissions and how to remove greenhouse gases from the atmosphere (from the air).

How to reduce climate change everywhere.

Global impacts and effects of climate change.

Personal actions I can take to help mitigating (reduce) climate change.

17. Is there anything you wish you had **more scientific knowledge** about? Something you want to **know more about**? Which **major question(s)** would you expect the **next IPCC reports** to address?

18. **Did you know** this IPCC material? You can take your time to briefly read them, if you want, by clicking on the link. *

Yes, I used it/ read it

Yes

The **Summary for Policymaker**

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_SYR_SPM.pdf

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_WGI_SPM.pdf

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_WGI_I_SummaryForPolicymakers.pdf

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_WGI_II_SummaryForPolicymakers.pdf

The **Frequently asked questions**

(FAQs)
<https://www.ipcc.ch/help/frequently-asked-questions/>

The **facts sheets**

<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/resources/factsheets/>

[/factsheets](#)
<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/about/factsheets/>
<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/resources/factsheets/>

The **interactive atlas**
<https://interactive-atlas.ipcc.ch/>

The **summary for all**
<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/resources/summary-for-all/>
https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/downloads/outreach/IPCC_AR6_WGI_I_SummaryForAll_Adaptation.pdf

The **report video**
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SDRxfuEvqGq>

19. If yes, do you find these documents **easy to understand**? Please indicate which document you are talking about.

20. Do you have any **suggestions** to make on these documents? Please indicate which document you are talking about.

21. According to you, what **other material** (kind of document) should IPCC use to **engage young people**? *

22. What are your **needs** in terms of **material** (documents: books, comics, summary for young people, videos, events, flyers..for example) and **scientific communication** (how do you want the IPCC to reach you, to communicate with young people about climate change) ?

Closing

Thank you very much for your participation and all your answers.

23. Is there anything else you want the IPCC to know?

24. When looking at your responses, we might want to get more information from your side. If you would agree to be contacted again, please give us your contact details (preferably your email address)

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Annex II - Graphics

Graphic 1 – Distribution of participants between the two versions of the questionnaire

distribution of the 643 participants between the two versions of the questionnaire

Graphic 2 - Distribution of respondents by gender

Graphic 3 – Distribution of respondents by age

NB: we cannot guarantee the truthfulness of participants' answers regarding their age.

Average age : 22.6

Average age : 23.7

Average age : 21.8

Graphic 4 – Distribution of respondents by region and citizenship

NB: 50 people in total have two or more nationalities.

North America, Central America, Caribbean

South America

South West Pacific

Europe

Graphic 5 – Distribution of respondents by region and country of residence
One person has two countries of residence.

Africa

Asia

North America, Central America, Caribbean

South West Pacific

South America

Europe

Graphic 6 – How did the respondents know about the survey?

Where was the questionnaire found ?

Number of English survey participants for each discovery place of the questionnaire

Number of French survey participants for each discovery place of the questionnaire

Graphic 7 – Are the respondents part of a youth organization?

Percentage of participants who belong to a youth organisation

Percentage of participants of the English survey who belong to a youth organisation

Percentage of participants of the French survey who belong to a youth organisation

Graphic 8 – Do respondents know the IPCC?

Percentage of participants who had heard about the IPCC

Percentage of participants of the English survey who had heard about the IPCC

Percentage of participants of the French survey who had heard about the IPCC

Graphic 9 – what do respondent know/don't know about the IPCC?

- 9) The IPCC does not organise the COPs (Conference of the Parties, it is an annual meeting about climate change, with governments from all over the world) but gives scientific information to the participants about climate change.
- 8) IPCC reports are neutral and do not make political stands or recommendations about climate change and its solutions.
- 7) IPCC experts and authors are from all over the world and there is a geographical balance, a gender equality and a diversity regarding previous experience and expertise.
- 6) Experts and authors who work on IPCC reports are not paid by the IPCC.
- 5) The IPCC does not conduct its own research. Experts and authors work to summarise what is known about climate change.
- 4) The IPCC prepares Assessment Reports (scientific document) about the state of scientific knowledge on climate change, its impacts and solutions to reduce climate change.
- 3) All the IPCC decisions are made by consensus (all the member countries need to agree).
- 2) The IPCC is an intergovernmental organisation and has 195 Member countries.
- 1) The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) is the United Nations body for collecting and evaluating the science related to climate change.

Total results for each information (as a percentage of participants)

English survey results for each information (as a percentage of participants)

French survey results for each information (as a percentage of participants)

Graphic 10 – Do you trust the scientific information provided by the IPCC?

0: not at all
10: yes, absolutely

Total results (as a percentage of participants)

English survey results

French survey results

Graphic 11 – Do you agree/not agree with the following statements?

- 7) I already experience the effects of climate change in my region.
- 6) I feel excited by all the opportunities that the climate crisis will offer.
- 5) I think I know enough about climate change and the science behind it.
- 4) I feel listened by the government/ the international organisations
- 3) I feel powerless in the face of climate change
- 2) Thinking about climate change impacts me emotionally/ makes me anxious
- 1) I am not worried at all about what my future will look like because of climate change. I feel confident about the future.

Total results for each affirmation (as a percentage of participants)

English survey results for each affirmation (as a percentage of participants)

French survey results for each affirmation (as a percentage of participants)

Graphic 12 – tone used (negative, neutral, positive) to answer to the question « how do you imagine your future life to be, from a climate point of view, in the region you live? »

Total percentage of projections by tone

Percentage of the English survey projections by tone

Percentage of the French survey projections by tone

NB: the categories were vague and the sorting was left to our discretion. The aim was to emphasise general tendencies, all the more general since a lot of answers could fit in several categories

Graphic 13 – Spread of the answers to the question *do the IPCC actions (reports, workshops and expert meetings information, communications, press release...) help you in your different activities or for your general knowledge?*

Answers range from 0 (absolutely not) to 10 (yes, definitely)

Total percentage of answers for each category

Percentage of answers for each category [English survey]

Percentage of answers for each category [French survey]

Graphic 14 – Topics respondents are the most interested in

- (6) - Personal actions I can take to help mitigating (reduce) climate change
- (5) - The science on past, present and future climate change
- (4) - How we can estimate the quantity of greenhouse gas emissions and how to remove greenhouse gases from the atmosphere (from the air)
- (3) - global impacts and effects of climate change
- (2) - The impacts of climate change on my region/city
- (1) - how to reduce climate change everywhere

Total rankings of each topic (as a percentage of participants)

English survey rankings of each topic

French survey rankings of each topic

Graphic 15 – Knowledge of the existence of IPCC material

Graphic 16 – How easy to understand is the IPCC material?

